

Comparative study of electrospray and photospray ionization sources coupled to quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometer for olive oil authentication

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Abstract

The use of fast and reliable analytical procedures for olive oil authentication is a priority demand due to its wide consumption and healthy benefits. Olive oil adulteration with other cheaper vegetable oils is a common practice that has to be detected and controlled. Rapid screening methods based on high resolution tandem mass spectrometry constitute today the option of choice due to sample handling simplicity and the elimination of the chromatographic step. The selection of the ionization source is critical and the comparison of their reliability necessary. The possibilities of the direct infusion electrospray ionization (ESI) and the recently introduced atmospheric pressure photospray ionization source (APPI), coupled to quadrupole time-of-flight (QqTOF), have been critically studied and compared to control olive oil adulteration. These techniques are very rapid (approximately 1 min per sample) and have high discrimination power to elucidate key components in the edible oils studied (olive, hazelnut, sunflower and corn). Nevertheless, both sources are complementary, being APPI more sensitive for monoacyl- and diacylglycerol fragment ions and ESI for triacylglycerols. In addition, methods reproducibility's are very high, especially for APPI source. Mixtures of olive oil with the others vegetable oils can be easily discriminated which has been tested by using principal components analysis (PCA) with both ESI-MS and APPI-MS spectra. Analogously, linear discriminant analysis (LDA) confirms methods reproducibility and detection of other oils used as adulterants, in particular hazelnut oil, which is especially difficult given its chemical similarity with olive oil.

Keywords: Atmospheric pressure photoionization; Electrospray ionization; Quadrupole time-of-flight; Olive oil authentication; Fingerprinting

1. Introduction

Olive oil is one of the most important ingredients of the so-called Mediterranean diet, used for frying, roasting and seasoning. Medical and epidemiological research conducted under the auspices of the International Olive Oil Council have demonstrated the benefits of eating olive oil in cardiovascular [1] and diabetes [2] diseases, as well as in bone and nervous system development [3,4]. In addition, it has been proved its antioxidant and anti-aging properties at cell and mitochondrial levels [5], as well as the general favorable action of this food-stuff on the nutrition and diet. For these reasons, olive oil is one of the most consumed edible vegetable oils and it is particularly expensive, which may present the opportunity for producers to stretch their merchandise by adulterating it with cheaper vegetable oils of lower quality [6]. The situation is especially critical for hazelnut oil adulteration due to its high similitude in chemical composition with olive oil. This fact makes difficult the use of triacylglycerols (TAGs), which are considered to be good fingerprints for adulteration detection purposes [7].

Olive oil fingerprinting is usually accomplished by NMR [8], Raman [9,10], pyrolysis-MS [11], GC-MS [12] or direct HS-MS techniques [12]. However, more rapid, accurate, reliable and robust analytical methodologies are being requested for olive oil authentication, to be suitable for routine analysis.

Recent developments in mass spectrometry makes possible to fulfill these requirements, because of the high resolution reached with tandem mass spectrometry (triple quadrupole QqQ, quadrupole time-of-flight QqTOF and others) avoids chromato-

graphic separation and reduces the analysis time and sample preparation significantly. These analytical tools allow fingerprinting in complex food matrices as olive oil and provide useful information about all the components present in the sample. Goodacre et al. [13] reported the use of ESI-MS technique in olive oil authentication, showing that information-rich spectra from vegetable and nut oils can be generated without chromatographic separation. This spectral information allows the discrimination of olive oil from others commonly used as adulterants, particularly hazelnut oil. Latterly, Gómez-Ariza et al.

[14] described the employ of the atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI) [15,16] source for this purpose, considering its suitability to ionize analytes with little or no polarity. In addition, the APPI source can suffer less matrix effects because of its specificity towards the analytes which form the molecular radical ion M^+ . However, both sources are complementary, because the ionization pattern of ESI based in the formation of ammonium adducts $[M-NH_4]^+$ [13] changes in APPI to the production of $[M+H]^+$ and $[M]^+$ ions of key compounds [14], as well as the ion $[R_1CO-H_2O]^+$ formed by the loss of water from the acylium ion. This latter ion is absent in the ESI-MS spectra.

Therefore, a comparison of both sources considering their discrimination capability on several highly consumed edible oils and their mixtures is necessary, especially for olive and hazelnut oils. The use of ESI-MS for the analysis of several oils including corn, grapestone, pomace, olive, extra virgin olive, peanut, soya, sunflower oils and a mixed oil comprising peanut, sunflower and soya oils has been previously considered [13]. However, the analysis of mixtures including olive oil which could provide information about the adulteration level of this food remains unknown. In addition, under our knowledge the system APPI-MS has not been used for this purpose.

The aim of the present work is the application of ESI-MS and APPI-MS systems for the discrimination of edible oils and mixtures to deep insight into the complementary use of both sources.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and sample preparation

Oil samples [olive oil (O), hazelnut oil (H), sunflower oil (S) and corn oil (C)] were supplied by Olibeas cooperative (Huelva, Spain) and stored at 4 °C.

The solvents, HPLC-grade, dichloromethane, methanol and toluene, were purchased from Teknokroma (Barcelona, Spain), and the ammonium acetate was supplied by Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Water was purified with a Milli-Q Gradient system (Millipore, Watford, UK).

All oils were 1000-fold diluted with a mixture of 60% dichloromethane: 40% 10 mM ammonium acetate in methanol when the ESI source was used. For APPI dilution was performed with dichloromethane/methanol (60:40, v/v).

Oil mixtures were prepared at 90, 70 and 50 (v/v) of olive oil with hazelnut, sunflower and corn oils, separately. Prior to infusion these mixtures were dissolved in the solution described above.

2.2. Instrumentation

2.2.1. ESI-QqTOF

The samples were loaded into a 100 μL volume Hamilton gastight syringe mounted into an integrated apparatus pump operating at a flow rate of 5 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ and introduced directly into an API QSTAR[®] XL Hybrid system (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA).

All data were obtained in positive ion mode (ES^+). The TAGs were identified by the molecular ion mass spectra. Averaged spectra in full-scan mode were acquired for 1 min in the m/z range 100–2000 with 1.005 s scan time. The resolution for the Q1 region was fixed at unit mass resolution.

The parameters of the QqTOF system were optimized for analysis with the source electrospray ionization (ESI). The ion-spray voltage (IS) was finally set at 3000 V, the source and desolvation temperatures were both 60 °C with a declustering potential (DP) fixed at 76 V and focusing potential (FP) at 230 V (the orifice (OR) and focusing ring (RNG) voltages control the amount of declustering and fragmentation in the orifice-skimmer region of the vacuum interface). The curtain gas (CUR) was set at 1.13 L min^{-1} and the nebulizer gas (UHP 99.999% nitrogen) was finally optimized at 1.56 L min^{-1} for signal stability and sensitivity.

The ion energy (IE) was fixed at 2.0 V with a channel electron multiplier (CEM) of 2250 V.

ESI-MS-MS spectra were acquired by using nitrogen as the collision gas, the collision energy was set at 50–60 eV, and both the quadrupole (Q) and TOF analyzers were employed. Other conditions were the same as for the MS analysis described above.

2.2.2. APPI-QqTOF

The instrumental conditions used with this system were described elsewhere [14]. Briefly in this study was used, flow injection analysis (FIA) for sample introduction in the APPI-QqTOF. It was performed using an Agilent 1100 series HPLC provided with a binary pump and autosampler. A model KDS 100 syringe pump from KD scientific (New Hope, PA, USA) was used to deliver the dopant to the APPI ion source. This instrument was connected to an API QSTAR[®] XL Hybrid system (Applied Biosystems) fitted with an atmospheric pressure

photoionization source. This ion source made use of a heated nebulizer (HN), whose heater was maintained at 350 °C for all these experiments. Nitrogen was used to nebulize the liquid eluant (nebulizer gas) and also to transport the finely dispersed sample drops through the heated quartz tube in which they were vaporized (auxiliary gas).

The operation conditions were the following: the flow rate provided by LC pumps was fixed at 0.5 mL min^{-1} using 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol as LC eluant. A 5 μL loop was used in the injector of the autosampler. The dopant (toluene) was delivered at 0.05 mL min^{-1} .

All data were obtained in positive ion mode. Averaged spectra in full-scan mode were acquired in the m/z range 100–1100.

The parameters of the QqTOF system were optimized for the analysis with the source APPI. The capillary voltage was finally set at 1500 V, with a DP fixed at 85 V and FP at 300 V. The IE was at 2.0 V with a CEM of 2300 V. So that, the CUR was finally set at 1.13 L min^{-1} , and the nebulizer gas optimized at 1.50 L min^{-1} with the heater gas at 6.0 L min^{-1} . This gas assists solvent evaporation and increases the ionization of the sample.

2.2.3. Chemometrics

Computations were performed by using the statistical pack-age STATISTICA Version 6.0 (2001) (StatSoft, Tulsa, USA). Principal components analysis (PCA) and linear discriminant

Fig. 1. Full-scan ESI-MS: (a) olive oil and (b) hazelnut oil. The region between m/z 800 and 900 is magnified.

Fig. 2. Full-scan ESI-MS: (a) sunflower oil and (b) corn oil. The region between m/z 800 and 900 is magnified.

analysis (LDA) were applied to the relative abundance of peaks in the mass spectra obtained from both ESI- and APPI-QqTOF.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. ESI and APPI mass spectra

ESI-MS spectrum (Fig. 1) of olive oil is dominated by a peak at m/z 903 that can be matched with a similar peak in the hazelnut oil spectrum. This peak can be attributed to the ammonium adduct $[M + NH_4]^+$ of triolein (trioleoylglycerol, OOO), which is the most abundant triacylglycerol in both olive and hazelnut oils [13]. The spectra of both edible oils are very similar (Fig. 1), although the peak at m/z 897, caused by trilinoleoyl-glycerol (LLL), is only detected in hazelnut oil and can be used as a marker for olive oil adulteration assessment [17]. For sunflower and corn oils (Fig. 2) the most abundant peak lies at m/z 899 originated by the ammonium adduct of 1,2-dilinoleoyl-3-oleoylglycerol (LLO). Table 1 summarizes the most abundant triacylglycerols in the different oils under study.

Fig. 2 shows that LLL ammonium adducts (m/z 897) are the second prominent peak in the APPI-MS spectra of sunflower and corn oils. An additional difference between these oils is the presence in sunflower of 1,2-dilinoleoyl-3-behenoylglycerol (BLL), m/z 957, Table 1.

The m/z values of significant peaks in the MS/MS spectra from above mentioned ions are shown in Table 2. The major daughter ions from the precursor ion at m/z 903 (OOO) are observed at m/z 603 $[OO]^+$ and m/z 265 acylium ion of the oleic acid fatty acyl, in both olive and hazelnut oils. The MS/MS spectrum of LLL, characteristic in hazelnut oil shows two peaks at m/z 599 $[LL]^+$ and m/z 263 acylium ion of the linoleic acid

Table 1

Mains TAGs identified in the ESI-QqTOF mass spectra of four vegetables oils TAGs $[M + NH_4]^+$ (m/z) Olive Hazelnut Sunflower Corn

TAG	m/z	Olive	Hazelnut	Sunflower	Corn
OOO	903	✓	✓	✓	✓
POO	877	✓	✓	✓	✓
LOO	901	✓	✓	✓	✓
PLO	875	✓	✓	✓	✓
PPO	851	✓	n.d	✓	✓
OOS	905	✓	n.d	✓	✓
LLO	899	✓	✓	✓	✓
POPo	848	✓	n.d	✓	✓
LLL	897	n.d	✓	✓	✓
LLP	878	n.d	n.d	✓	✓
SOP	879	✓	✓	✓	✓
BLL	956	n.d	n.d	✓	n.d

OOO, 1,2,3-trioleoylglycerol; POO, dioleoyl-1-palmitoilylglycerol; LOO, 2,3- dioleoyl-1-linoleoylglycerol; PLO, 1-palmitoyl-2-linoleyl-3-oleylglycerol; PPO, 1,2-dipalmitoyl-3-stearoylglycerol; OOS, 1,2-dioleoyl-3-stearoylglycerol; LLO, 1,2-dilinoleoyl-3-oleylglycerol; POPo, 1-palmitoyl-2-oleyl-3- palmitoilylglycerol; LLL, 1,2,3-trilinoleoylglycerol; LLP, 1,2-dilinoleoyl-3- palmitoilylglycerol; LLLn, 1,2-dilinoleoyl-3-linolenylglycerol; LnLP, 1-linolenyl-2-linoleyl-3-palmitoilylglycerol; SOP, 2-oleyl-3-palmitoyl-1-stearoylglycerol

and BLL, 1,2-dilinoleoyl-3-behenoylglycerol. ✓, detected; n.d, not detected.

Table 2

Masses of the characteristic fragment ions A and fragment ions C of triacylglycerols using the ESI-MS/MS

TAGs	Ion A	$[M-R_1CO]^+$ (m/z)	Ion C	$[R_1CO]^+$ (m/z)
OOO	OO	603	O	265
LLL	LL	599	L	263
LLO	OL	601	P	239
PPO	PO	577	Po	237
POPo	PoO	575	Ln	261
PLO	PL	575	B	323
LLLn	LLn	597	S	267
BLL	BL	659	–	–
SOP	SO	605	–	–

fatty acyl. In sunflower and corn oils the MS/MS spectrum of the precursor ion m/z 899 LLO shows two daughter ions at m/z 601 $[LO]^+$ and m/z 263 acylium ion previously mentioned. The MS/MS spectrum of BLL in sunflower oil exhibits ions at m/z 660 $[BL]^+$, m/z 599 $[LL]^+$ and m/z 263 this latter above mentioned.

Results from the full-scan APPI- and ESI-MS confirm the presence of $[M+H]^+$, $[M]^+$, $[R_iCO]^+$ and $[R_iCO-H_2O]^+$ ions in the former [14] and $[M+NH_4]^+$ adducts in the later [13]. The higher abundance of diacylglycerol (DAG) and monoacylglycerol (MAG) in the APPI-MS [14] than in ESI-MS (Fig. 3) is also remarkable.

Fig. 4 shows the full-scan APPI mass spectra for the sunflower and corn oils, which exhibit significant differences with those corresponding to olive and hazelnut oils. The most abundant peak from sunflower and corn oils using the APPI source is that from monoacylglycerol at m/z 337 $[L]^+$, while in olive and hazelnut oils (Fig. 5), is the m/z 339 $[O]^+$.

Fig. 3. Fragmentation of triacylglycerols (TAGs), diacylglycerols (DAGs) and monoacylglycerols (MAGs), using positive ion APPI. A–D are the most important fragment ions.

Fig. 4. Full-scan APPI-MS: (a) sunflower oil and (b) corn oil. The region between m/z 800 and 900 is magnified.

Fig. 5. Full-scan APPI-MS: (a) olive oil and (b) hazelnut oil. The region between m/z 800 and 900 is magnified.

Table 3
Relative abundance TAG (%) of hazelnut, sunflower, corn, olive oil and their mixtures obtained from the ESI-QqTOF

Sample	OOO	POO	LOO	PLO	PPO	OOS	LLO	POPo	LLL	LLP	LLLn	LnLP	SOP	BLL
O	26.92 ± 0.52	21.74 ± 0.19	11.76 ± 0.22	7.77 ± 0.18	3.94 ± 0.07	15.32 ± 0.06	3.13 ± 0.09	1.34 ± 0.03	n.d	1.52 ± 0.02	0.07 ± 0.05	0.16 ± 0.01	5.98 ± 0.31	n.d
H	31.16 ± 0.63	16.57 ± 0.14	18.23 ± 0.20	4.35 ± 0.13	0.34 ± 0.06	16.91 ± 0.19	5.37 ± 0.13	n.d	1.44 ± 0.07	0.89 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01	n.d	3.54 ± 0.18	0.16 ± 0.01
S	11.45 ± 0.03	5.01 ± 0.01	17.31 ± 0.04	8.23 ± 0.04	0.54 ± 0.03	2.59 ± 0.02	21.01 ± 0.13	0.88 ± 0.01	18.71 ± 0.09	9.72 ± 0.08	0.41 ± 0.01	0.33 ± 0.06	0.86 ± 0.07	2.94 ± 0.07
C	7.95 ± 0.23	6.26 ± 0.09	15.12 ± 0.01	12.75 ± 0.14	1.44 ± 0.01	1.66 ± 0.05	18.47 ± 0.30	2.43 ± 0.04	16.32 ± 0.05	13.52 ± 0.10	1.28 ± 0.02	0.80 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.06
O:H (90:10)	28.64 ± 0.20	19.96 ± 0.48	8.75 ± 0.10	4.65 ± 0.05	2.32 ± 0.02	12.82 ± 0.13	2.18 ± 0.09	0.84 ± 0.01	0.39 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.01	n.d	0.10 ± 0.03	4.27 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.07
O:H (70:30)	29.87 ± 0.28	18.84 ± 0.23	9.33 ± 0.05	4.26 ± 0.03	2.02 ± 0.02	12.93 ± 0.16	2.33 ± 0.04	0.71 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.01	n.d	0.10 ± 0.13	4.13 ± 0.19	0.13 ± 0.02
O:H (50:50)	30.21 ± 0.33	16.78 ± 0.29	10.61 ± 0.03	3.77 ± 0.03	1.58 ± 0.02	13.04 ± 0.14	2.58 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.14	0.59 ± 0.02	0.80 ± 0.14	n.d	0.35 ± 0.02	3.46 ± 0.08	0.14 ± 0.02
O:S (90:10)	34.58 ± 0.67	18.47 ± 0.07	10.52 ± 0.18	5.34 ± 0.09	2.05 ± 0.02	10.68 ± 0.11	7.04 ± 0.01	0.82 ± 0.04	3.93 ± 0.05	2.22 ± 0.07	n.d	0.14 ± 0.03	3.67 ± 0.01	0.55 ± 0.20
O:S (70:30)	28.17 ± 0.11	14.79 ± 0.18	12.50 ± 0.04	5.60 ± 0.03	1.67 ± 0.05	8.31 ± 0.16	12.35 ± 0.03	0.81 ± 0.01	8.08 ± 0.05	3.48 ± 0.04	0.17 ± 0.01	0.17 ± 0.01	2.88 ± 0.07	1.02 ± 0.03
O:S (50:50)	23.23 ± 0.10	11.59 ± 0.31	14.18 ± 0.07	5.78 ± 0.06	1.28 ± 0.04	6.64 ± 0.10	16.42 ± 0.18	0.73 ± 0.01	11.55 ± 0.13	4.47 ± 0.06	0.21 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.01	2.35 ± 0.03	1.37 ± 0.03
O:C (90:10)	34.61 ± 0.27	19.41 ± 0.08	9.74 ± 0.11	6.25 ± 0.06	2.34 ± 0.07	11.18 ± 0.04	5.41 ± 0.03	1.07 ± 0.01	2.80 ± 0.02	2.77 ± 0.03	0.23 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.01	3.79 ± 0.10	0.21 ± 0.01
O:C (70:30)	25.44 ± 5.11	14.63 ± 0.19	11.65 ± 0.05	8.25 ± 0.05	1.96 ± 0.05	7.56 ± 0.09	11.52 ± 0.14	1.35 ± 0.03	7.59 ± 0.05	6.08 ± 0.05	0.49 ± 0.05	0.33 ± 0.01	2.72 ± 0.01	0.44 ± 0.12
O:C (50:50)	24.12 ± 0.07	13.58 ± 0.12	12.05 ± 0.01	8.55 ± 0.07	1.85 ± 0.01	6.98 ± 0.04	12.41 ± 0.06	1.35 ± 0.01	8.50 ± 0.07	6.67 ± 0.09	0.54 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.02	2.54 ± 0.12	0.48 ± 0.02

Olive oil (O); hazelnut oil (H); sunflower oil (S); corn oil (C); olive oil–hazelnut oil (O:H) 90:10; olive oil–hazelnut oil (O:H) 70:30; olive oil–hazelnut oil (O:H) 50:50; olive oil–sunflower (O:S) 90:10; olive oil–sunflower oil (O:S) 70:30; olive oil–sunflower oil (O:S) 50:50; olive oil–corn oil (O:C) 90:10; olive oil–corn oil (O:C) 70:30; olive oil–corn oil (O:C) 50:50. Average of three determinations ± standard deviation(S.D.). n.d, not detected.

Table 4
Fragment ions of mono-, di-, triacylglycerols and acylium ions [R_nCO]⁺ relative abundance (%) the mass spectra obtained from APPI-QqTOF, for hazelnut, sunflower, corn, olive oil and their mixture

Sample	OOO	LLL	LLO	OO	OL	LL	OP	L	P	O	Ln	[RCO] ⁺ O	[RCO] ⁺ L	[RCO–H ₂ O] ⁺ O	[RCO–H ₂ O] ⁺ L
O	5.14 ± 0.45	n.d	1.84 ± 0.13	23.75 ± 1.17	8.67 ± 0.50	1.64 ± 0.17	16.32 ± 0.70	5.01 ± 0.47	6.24 ± 0.22	25.15 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.16	3.22 ± 0.05	0.66 ± 0.04	1.21 ± 0.04	0.41 ± 0.04
H	6.23 ± 0.13	0.57 ± 0.01	1.45 ± 0.04	28.88 ± 0.08	8.43 ± 0.09	1.05 ± 0.06	11.41 ± 0.22	4.57 ± 0.12	3.40 ± 0.18	28.31 ± 0.41	0.19 ± 0.02	3.29 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.01	1.22 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.01
S	1.95 ± 0.20	4.82 ± 0.07	5.97 ± 0.16	14.56 ± 0.71	12.11 ± 0.53	8.55 ± 0.43	6.68 ± 0.11	17.59 ± 0.53	4.10 ± 0.43	17.32 ± 0.11	0.49 ± 0.53	1.77 ± 0.15	2.22 ± 0.62	0.69 ± 0.02	1.22 ± 0.02
C	1.37 ± 0.09	4.84 ± 0.21	5.95 ± 0.16	11.82 ± 0.42	13.60 ± 0.20	8.70 ± 0.01	9.18 ± 0.36	16.92 ± 0.07	6.75 ± 0.38	15.09 ± 0.18	0.65 ± 0.01	1.41 ± 0.01	2.03 ± 0.01	0.57 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.03
O:H1	4.37 ± 0.15	0.38 ± 0.17	1.45 ± 0.09	25.72 ± 0.17	6.17 ± 0.03	1.00 ± 0.09	15.19 ± 0.38	3.68 ± 0.07	5.44 ± 0.01	27.29 ± 0.09	0.30 ± 0.01	2.83 ± 0.01	0.53 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.01	0.32 ± 0.01
O:H2	5.15 ± 0.12	0.56 ± 0.01	1.10 ± 0.02	27.06 ± 0.53	6.75 ± 0.18	0.78 ± 0.02	13.87 ± 0.06	3.98 ± 0.03	5.09 ± 0.06	29.12 ± 0.21	0.24 ± 0.01	3.92 ± 0.10	0.62 ± 0.02	1.40 ± 0.03	0.35 ± 0.01
O:H3	5.43 ± 0.03	0.60 ± 0.19	0.99 ± 0.01	29.04 ± 0.19	6.93 ± 0.23	0.83 ± 0.05	13.10 ± 0.35	4.02 ± 0.05	5.02 ± 0.05	30.70 ± 0.35	0.23 ± 0.01	4.32 ± 0.08	0.64 ± 0.01	1.56 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.01
O:S1	4.60 ± 0.24	0.44 ± 0.02	1.31 ± 0.01	27.87 ± 0.24	6.62 ± 0.06	1.03 ± 0.02	16.20 ± 0.11	3.57 ± 0.05	5.36 ± 0.15	27.14 ± 0.36	0.27 ± 0.01	3.35 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.01	1.28 ± 0.02	0.37 ± 0.03
O:S2	3.68 ± 0.09	2.07 ± 0.06	3.08 ± 0.07	22.02 ± 0.54	8.35 ± 0.25	3.71 ± 0.27	13.92 ± 0.03	8.35 ± 0.36	5.33 ± 0.02	23.40 ± 0.24	0.33 ± 0.06	2.92 ± 0.01	1.08 ± 0.01	1.12 ± 0.05	0.64 ± 0.41
O:S3	3.63 ± 0.35	2.97 ± 0.04	4.04 ± 0.01	20.11 ± 0.70	9.24 ± 0.22	5.01 ± 0.28	12.85 ± 0.10	10.20 ± 0.28	5.08 ± 0.04	20.87 ± 0.31	0.43 ± 0.14	2.54 ± 0.02	1.30 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	0.73 ± 0.01
O:C1	4.11 ± 0.01	0.53 ± 0.03	1.37 ± 0.04	25.68 ± 0.08	6.83 ± 0.04	1.30 ± 0.03	16.66 ± 0.04	4.10 ± 0.08	6.15 ± 0.03	26.99 ± 0.10	0.31 ± 0.01	3.60 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.02	1.36 ± 0.10	0.39 ± 0.10
O:C2	4.10 ± 0.06	1.86 ± 0.11	2.67 ± 0.05	22.98 ± 0.31	8.74 ± 0.18	3.54 ± 0.17	15.39 ± 0.02	7.14 ± 0.25	5.77 ± 0.05	21.92 ± 0.29	0.34 ± 0.01	2.91 ± 0.07	0.98 ± 0.02	1.09 ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.01
O:C3	3.37 ± 0.09	2.45 ± 0.04	3.36 ± 0.01	20.99 ± 0.24	9.79 ± 0.10	4.65 ± 0.08	14.26 ± 0.07	9.24 ± 0.22	5.89 ± 0.06	20.15 ± 0.17	0.39 ± 0.01	2.56 ± 0.07	1.23 ± 0.04	0.96 ± 0.02	0.70 ± 0.01

Olive oil (O); hazelnut oil (H); sunflower oil (S); corn oil (C); olive oil–hazelnut oil (O:H1) 90:10; olive oil–hazelnut oil (O:H2) 70:30; olive oil–hazelnut oil (O:H3) 50:50; olive oil–sunflower (O:S1) 90:10; olive oil–sunflower oil (O:S2) 70:30; olive oil–sunflower oil (O:S3) 50:50; olive oil–corn oil (O:C1) 90:10; olive oil–corn oil (O:C2) 70:30; olive oil–corn oil (O:C3) 50:50. Fatty acid abbreviations: O, oleic (18:1), L, linoleic (18:2), P, palmitic (16:0), Ln, linolenic (18:3). Average of three determinations ± standard deviation (S.D.). n.d, not detected.

3.2. Oil mixtures study

In order to assess the possible adulteration of olive oil with the previously studied vegetable oils, several mixtures were performed as previously described (Section 2.1). As can be seen in Table 3, several triacylglycerols can be used as markers of the presence of hazelnut in olive oil, like OOO and LOO, when the ESI source is used. These compounds are present in both olive and hazelnut oils, although their relative abundance in the mass spectra is higher in the last (OOO, 31.16%; LOO, 18.23%) than those from olive oil (OOO, 26.92%; LOO, 11.76%). This difference can be appreciated in mixtures with hazelnut oil at percentages lower than 10%. In addition, LLL, which is not present in olive oil, is at 1.44% in the mass spectra from hazelnut oil and for this reason it can also be used to identify this adulteration. The adulteration of olive oil with sunflower and corn oils can be detected on the basis of LLO, which is the most abundant triacylglycerol in the former. Due to the low relative abundance of LLO in olive oil mass spectra, an increase of this peak can be used for this purpose. In this way, BLL is only present in a measurable abundance in sunflower oil.

When the APPI source is used (Table 4) significant differences can be pointed out between hazelnut and olive oils. Hazelnut oil mass spectra exhibit a higher relative abundance of OOO (6.23%), the fragment ion of DAG [OO]⁺ (28.88%) and of MAG [O]⁺ (28.31%). As commented previously, the presence of LLL in sunflower and corn oils and its absence in olive oil, can also be detected using the APPI source. Analogously, [LL]⁺ and [L]⁺ appear in the mass spectra of sunflower and corn oils with a higher relative abundance. Mixtures of olive oil with them are in good agreement with the previous results for the ESI source.

The APPI source allows more sensitive detection of monoacyl- and diacylglycerol fragment ions than ESI, which confers to the former additional advantages. However, both sources are complementary, since ESI is more suitable for the detection of triacylglycerols.

3.3. Principal component analysis

For a better understanding of the discriminating efficiency of the descriptors selected, a preliminary study based on principal component analysis has been carried out, despite of the a priori knowledge the class membership of the oil samples. PCA finds the maximum variations in the data set and forms new variables known as principal components (PCs) [18], such that each successive PC accounts for as much of the remaining variability as possible and each new variable must be totally independent of all other variables. In this case, PCA was applied to our data calculated according to the relative abundance (percentage) of each peak in the TIC, as a semiquantitative method.

For the ESI source, the abundance of TAG adducts (OOO, POO, LOO, PLO, PPO, OOS, LLO, POPo, LLL, LLP, LLLn, LnLP, SOP and BLL) in mass spectra of the oils were considered as variables, and each type of oil or mixture as a class. From the loadings of original variables in the two first considered principal components (Table 5), the dominant variables in the first principal component (PC1) representing 70.56% of the total variance are POO, LLO, LLL, LLP, OOS and OOO while PPO, POPo and LOO show the lower values of variance. The variables appear at negative and positive values of PC1 and PC2. From this fact, it could be inferred that they provide different type of information. Principal component two (PC2) explains up to 18.04% of the total variance. Examining the loadings PPO and POPo are the most dominant variables in PC2. The first two principal components account for 88.6% of the total variance and were considered to be sufficient for this study.

The resulting ordination plot from PCA on these oils and their mixtures samples with ESI source is shown in Fig. 6. It can be seen even from this simple PCA that clear separation in PCA space occurs between the three oils (hazelnut, sunflower and corn oil), which are clearly separated from olive oil. Moreover, the principal components analysis showed that the mixtures

Table 5
 Loadings of the variables for the two first principal components (PC's) using ESI and APPI sources

ESI			APPI		
Variable	PC1	PC2	Variable	PC1	PC2
OOO	-0.292	0.047	OOO	-0.255	-0.149
POO	-0.304	-0.159	LLL	0.277	-0.066
LOO	0.195	0.296	LLO	0.279	-0.031
PLO	0.260	-0.340	OO	-0.272	-0.089
PPO	-0.168	-0.462	OL	0.268	-0.033
OOS	-0.295	0.018	LL	0.280	-0.017
LLO	0.302	0.121	OP	-0.216	0.475
POPo	0.199	-0.483	L	0.279	-0.083
LLL	0.308	0.097	P	0.043	0.793
LLP	0.310	-0.121	O	-0.270	-0.132
LLLn	0.275	-0.243	Ln		
LnLP	0.248	-0.289	[RCO] oleic aci	-0.259	-0.041
SOP	-0.288	-0.185	[RCO] ⁺ linoleic acid	0.277	-0.097
BLL	0.239	0.322	[RCO-H ₂ O] ⁺ oleic acid	-0.252	-0.030
			[RCO-H ₂ O] ⁺ linoleic acid	0.277	-0.083

Fig. 6. Principal components analysis for (a) ESI-MS and (c) APPI-MS. Linear discriminant analysis for (b) ESI-MS and (d) APPI-MS.

(90% olive oil with 10% hazelnut and 90% olive oil with 10% corn oil) are the nearest in the PCA space to olive oil.

Similarly, PCA was applied to the data obtained with the APPI source. The relative abundance in the mass spectra corresponding to compounds, fragments and acylium ions (Table 4) from the different oils were considered as variables, and each type of oil or mixtures of them as classes.

Table 5 shows the first two principal components that were extracted. These typically accounted for >94% of the overall variance. Examining the score plot of the objects in the space defined by the two principal components considered (Fig. 6), it can be observed an evident separation of the four oils and their mixtures. These results were in good agreement with those obtained by the ESI source.

3.4. Linear discriminant analysis

Unsupervised techniques only have visualizing capabilities, so a supervised pattern recognition method such as linear discriminant analysis was performed with the purpose of obtaining classification rules to assign categories to samples.

After applying LDA, four discriminant functions were calculated. Fig. 6 shows the scatter plot of oils samples in the plane defined by the discriminant functions DF_1 and DF_2 . Seven different classes were correctly separated (olive oil, hazelnut oil, sun-flower oil, corn oil and their corresponding mixture 90:10 with olive oil). We analyzed the mixture 90:10 of different oils with olive oil, because this adulteration is the most difficult to detect. LDA using the relative abundance of TAGs as the variables showed that oils and their mixtures were clearly grouped according to their triacylglycerols composition. These results are consistent with other previously published data related to olive oil

[19].

Moreover, the pattern recognition method shows that the reproducibility of the analysis is very high, especially with the APPI source, and that olive oil can be clearly separated from other edible oils which could be used as adulterants.

4. Conclusions

The use of both ESI- and APPI-QqTOF represents a good alternative for edible oils fingerprinting. These couplings involving powerful ionization sources and highly discriminant mass analyzers, namely QqTOF-MS, provide a high resolution for multi-component matrices such as vegetable oils. These instrumental systems enable a very simple sample handling and high sample throughput, because no chromatographic separation is required. ESI and APPI sources are complementary on the basis of the higher sensitivity of ESI for triacylglycerols and APPI for monoacyl- and diacylglycerol fragment ions. Reproducibility of the analysis is very high but APPI provides better results. In addition, some fragments such as $[R\ CO-H\ O]^+$, corresponding to the loss of water from the acylium ion only can be detected by APPI-MS. Both ESI- and APPI-QqTOF can be used for olive oil adulteration diagnosis, because the discrimination from commonly used adulterants is allowed. The PCA of olive oil permits a safe evaluation of its authenticity and provides a precise classification of other edible oils and their mixtures. The application of LDA verifies methods reproducibility, especially with the APPI source, and gives additional evidences of the presence of adulterants.

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